

Neutrosophic Pseudo-t-Norm and Its Derived Neutrosophic Residual Implication

Hongru Bu ¹, Qingqing Hu ² and Xiaohong Zhang ^{3,*}

¹ School of Mathematics and Data Science, Shaanxi University of Science & Technology, Xi'an 710021, China; 221711026@sust.edu.cn

² School of Electrical and Control Engineering, Shaanxi University of Science & Technology, Xi'an 710021, China; bs1906001@sust.edu.cn

³ School of Mathematics and Data Science, Shaanxi University of Science and Technology, Xi'an 710021, China; zhangxiaohong@sust.edu.cn

* Correspondence: zhangxiaohong@sust.edu.cn; Tel.: 029-86168320

Abstract: First of all, on the basis of complete lattice, the concepts of neutrosophic pseudo-t-norms (NPTs) is given. Definitions and examples of representable neutrosophic pseudo-t-norms (RNPTs) are given, while unrepresentable neutrosophic pseudo-t-norms (UNPTs) is also given. Secondly, De Morgan neutrosophic triples (DMNTs) consists of three operators: NPTs, neutrosophic negators (NNs) and neutrosophic pseudo-s-norms (NPSs), where NPTs and NPSs are dual about NNs. Again, we study the neutrosophic residual implications (NRIs) of NPTs, as well as their underlying properties. Finally, we give a method to get NPTs from neutrosophic implications (NIs) and construct non-commutative residuated lattices (NCRLs) based on NRIs and NPTs.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Set; Neutrosophic Pseudo-t-Norm; Neutrosophic Residual Implication; Non-Commutative Residuated Lattices

1. Introduction

From the perspective of philosophy, Smarandache introduced neutrosophic sets (NSs). NSs is a expansion of fuzzy sets (FSs), and has universality [1]. Although NSs has expanded the expression of uncertain information, there are many inconveniences in practical application. From a scientific standpoint, so as to solve more practical problems, single valued neutrosophic sets (SVNSs) was put forward by Wang [2]. Some multi-attribute decision problems are solved by applying SVNSs. "SVNSs" is simply denoted as "NSs" in this article.

The t-norms, s-norms, negators, pseudo-t-norms, pseudo-s-norms and implications operators are fundamental tools in FS theory. Pseudo-t-norm and pseudo-s-norm was proposed in [3], followed by their residual implication were put forward by Wang in [4]. Pseudo-t-norm has many applications, such as resolution of finite fuzzy relation equations, linear optimization problems of mixed fuzzy relation inequalities and so on [5-10].

NSs has a lot of important neutrosophic logical operators, such as: NPTs, NPSs, NNs, NIs, NRIs and so on. In past few years, Smarandache [11] introduced n-conorm and n-norm in neutrosophic logic. Zhang et al. [12] introduced a new type of relation of inclusion for NSs. A new kind of residuated lattice obtained through neutrosophic t-norms and its derived NRIs was introduced by Hu and Zhang [13]. On the basis of neutrosophic t-norms, fuzzy reasoning triple I method was studied by Luo et al. [14]. Therefore, it is very meaningful to study the NRIs of NPTs.

The basic framework of this paper: Section 2 presents the basics knowledge that will be useful for writing this paper. We defined NPTs, NPSs, NNs and so on in Section 3. Moreover, we also provide some useful typical examples and theorems. In Section 4, the definitions of NRIs generated from NPTs are obtained, and their basic properties are discussed in depth. In addition, this paper provides a new method to generate NPTs from NIs, and at the same time prove that system $(D^*; \wedge_1, \vee_1, \otimes, \rightarrow, \neg, 0_{D^*}, 1_{D^*})$ is a NCRL. Section 5 concludes the whole content of this paper.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 ([3]) A mapping $PT: [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a pseudo-t-norm iff, $\forall m, n, r \in [0, 1]$:

- (PT1) $PT(m, PT(n, r)) = PT(n, PT(m, r))$;
- (PT2) if $m \leq n$, then $PT(m, r) \leq PT(n, r)$, $PT(r, m) \leq PT(r, n)$;
- (PT3) $PT(1, m) = m$, $PT(m, 1) = m$.

Definition 2.2 ([3]) A mapping $PS: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a pseudo-s-norm iff, $\forall m, n, r \in [0, 1]$:

- (PS1) $PS(m, PS(n, r)) = PS(n, PS(m, r))$;
- (PS2) if $m \leq n$, then $PS(m, r) \leq PS(n, r)$, $PS(r, m) \leq PS(r, n)$;
- (PS3) $PS(0, m) = m$, $PS(m, 0) = m$.

Definition 2.3 ([15]) An intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) W in nonempty set M is depicted through two mappings: $\mu_W(m)$ and $\nu_W(m): M \rightarrow [0, 1]$. W is expressed as, when $\forall m \in M$,

$$W = \{ \langle m, \mu_W(m), \nu_W(m) \rangle \mid m \in M \},$$

satisfy $0 \leq \mu_W(m) + \nu_W(m) \leq 1$, where $\mu_W(m)$ is affiliation function, $\nu_W(m)$ is non-affiliation function.

Definition 2.4 ([2]) Let the set M be nonempty. A SVN W in M is depicted through $T_W(x)$, $I_W(x)$, and $F_W(x)$, all of which are functions defined on $[0, 1]$. Then, W is expressed as, when $\forall m \in M$,

$$W = \{ \langle m, T_W(m), I_W(m), F_W(m) \rangle \mid m \in M \},$$

satisfy $0 \leq T_W(m) + I_W(m) + F_W(m) \leq 3$, where $T_W(m)$ is the function of truth-affiliation, $I_W(m)$ is the function of indeterminacy- affiliation, and $F_W(m)$ is the function of falsity- affiliation.

Proposition 2.5 ([13]) The first type of inclusion relationship is discussed in this article.

Definition 2.6 ([1,17,18]) Let the set M be nonempty. Give two NSs W, N in M , where $W = \{ \langle m, T_W(m), I_W(m), F_W(m) \rangle \mid m \in M \}$, $N = \{ \langle m, T_N(m), I_N(m), F_N(m) \rangle \mid m \in M \}$. The algebraic operations of the first type of inclusion relation was given as shown below, $\forall m \in M$:

- (1) $W \subseteq_1 N \Leftrightarrow T_W(m) \leq T_N(m), I_W(m) \geq I_N(m), F_W(m) \geq F_N(m)$;
- (2) $W \cup_1 N = \{ \langle m, \max(T_W(m), T_N(m)), \min(I_W(m), I_N(m)), \min(F_W(m), F_N(m)) \rangle \mid m \in M \}$;
- (3) $W \cap_1 N = \{ \langle m, \min(T_W(m), T_N(m)), \max(I_W(m), I_N(m)), \max(F_W(m), F_N(m)) \rangle \mid m \in M \}$;
- (4) $W^c = \{ \langle x, I_W(m), 1 - F_W(m), T_W(m) \rangle \mid m \in M \}$.

Proposition 2.7 ([13]) We consider that set D^* defined by,

$$D^* = \{ m = (m_1, m_2, m_3) \mid m_1, m_2, m_3 \in [0, 1] \}.$$

$\forall m, n \in D^*$, the order relation we define \leq_1 on D^* is shown below:

$$m \leq_1 n \Leftrightarrow m_1 \leq n_1, m_2 \geq n_2, m_3 \geq n_3.$$

Proposition 2.8 ([13]) $(D^*; \leq_1)$ is a partially ordered set.

Proposition 2.9 ([13]) $\forall m, n \in D^*, m \wedge_1 n$ is called maximum lower bound of m, n , and expressed as $\inf(m, n)$; $m \vee_1 n$ is called minimum upper bound of m, n , and expressed as $\sup(m, n)$. In other word, $(D^*; \leq_1)$ is a lattice.

The content of definition of operators \wedge_1 and \vee_1 refers to proposition 2 in [13].

Proposition 2.10 ([13]) $(D^*; \leq_1)$ is a complete lattice.

The maximum of D^* is indicated as $1_{D^*} = (1, 0, 0)$, the minimum of D^* is indicated as $0_{D^*} = (0, 1, 1)$.

Definition 2.11 ([16]) A pseudo-t-norm $PT: L \times L \rightarrow L$ on $(L; \leq_1)$ be undecreasing and associative mapping that meets $PT(1_L, m) = m = PT(m, 1_L)$, which $\forall m \in L$. A pseudo-s-norm $PS: L^2 \rightarrow L$ on $(L; \leq_1)$ be associative and undecreasing mapping that meets $PS(0_L, m) = m = PS(m, 0_L)$, $\forall m \in L$.

Definition 2.12 ([13]) For every $m \in D^*$, we define a complement of m as follows:

$$m^c = (m_3, 1 - m_2, m_1).$$

Proposition 2.13 ([13]) The system $(D^*; \wedge_1, \vee_1, ^c, 0_{D^*}, 1_{D^*})$ is a De Morgan algebra.

3. NPTs On $(D^*; \leq_1)$

Definition 3.1 A binary function $PT: D^* \times D^* \rightarrow D^*$ is called NPT, $\forall m, n, u, v, r \in D^*$, if PT satisfies:

(NPT1) $PT(m, PT(n, r)) = PT(n, PT(m, r))$;

(NPT2) $PT(m, n) \leq_1 PT(u, v)$ and $PT(n, m) \leq_1 PT(v, u)$, where $m \leq_1 u, n \leq_1 v$;

(NPT3) $PT(1_{D^*}, m) = m, PT(m, 1_{D^*}) = m$.

Definition 3.2 A binary function $PS: D^* \times D^* \rightarrow D^*$ is called NPS, $\forall m, n, u, v, r \in D^*$, if PS satisfies:

(NPS1) $PS(m, PS(n, r)) = PS(n, PS(m, r))$;

(NPS2) $PS(m, n) \leq_1 PS(u, v)$ and $PS(n, m) \leq_1 PS(v, u)$, where $m \leq_1 u, n \leq_1 v$;

(NPS3) $PS(0_{D^*}, m) = m, PS(m, 0_{D^*}) = m$.

Example 3.3 ([3,19]) Table 1 below gives part pseudo-t-norms, and its derived residual implications.

Table 1. Example of part pseudo-t-norms

Pseudo-t-norms	Residual implications
$PT_1(m, n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \in [0, a_1], n \in [0, b_1], \\ \min(m, n) & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$ <p>where $0 < a_1 < b_1 < 1$.</p>	$I_{1L}(m, n) = \begin{cases} \max(a_1, n) & \text{if } m \leq b_1, m > n, \\ n & \text{if } m > b_1, m > n, \\ 1 & \text{if } m \leq n. \end{cases}$ $I_{1R}(m, n) = \begin{cases} b_1 & \text{if } m \leq a_1, m > n, \\ n & \text{if } m > a_1, m > n, \\ 1 & \text{if } m \leq n. \end{cases}$
$PT_2(m, n) = \begin{cases} \min(m, n) & \text{if } \sin(\frac{\pi}{2}m) + n > 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } \sin(\frac{\pi}{2}m) + n \leq 1. \end{cases}$	$I_{2L}(m, n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \leq n, \\ \max\{n, \frac{2}{\pi} \arcsin(1 - m)\} & \text{if } m > n. \end{cases}$ $I_{2R}(m, n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \leq n, \\ \max\{n, 1 - \sin(\frac{\pi}{2}m)\} & \text{if } m > n. \end{cases}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 PT_3(m,n) &= \begin{cases} \min(m,n) & \text{if } m^2 + n^3 > 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } m^2 + n^3 \leq 1. \end{cases} & I_{3L}(m,n) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \leq n, \\ \max\{n, \sqrt{1-m^3}\} & \text{if } m > n. \end{cases} \\
 PT_4(m,n) &= \begin{cases} \min(m,n) & \text{if } m + \sqrt{n} > 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } m + \sqrt{n} \leq 1. \end{cases} & I_{3R}(m,n) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \leq n, \\ \max\{n, \sqrt[3]{1-m^2}\} & \text{if } m > n. \end{cases} \\
 & & I_{4L}(m,n) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \leq n, \\ \max\{n, 1-\sqrt{m}\} & \text{if } m > n. \end{cases} \\
 & & I_{4R}(m,n) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \leq n, \\ \max\{n, (1-m)^2\} & \text{if } m > n. \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 3.4 Table 2 below gives part pseudo-s-norms, and its derived residual co-implications.

Table 2. Example of part pseudo-s-norms

Pseudo-s-norms		Residual co-implications	
$PS_1(m,n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \geq a_1, n \geq b_1, \\ \max(m,n) & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$		$J_{1L}(m,n) = \begin{cases} a_1 & \text{if } m > b_1, m < n, \\ n & \text{if } m \leq b_1, m < n, \\ 0 & \text{if } m \geq n. \end{cases}$	
where $0 < a_1 < b_1 < 1$.		$J_{1R}(m,n) = \begin{cases} \min(a_1, n) & \text{if } m > a_1, m < n, \\ n & \text{if } m \leq a_1, m < n, \\ 0 & \text{if } m \geq n. \end{cases}$	
$PS_2(m,n) = \begin{cases} \max(m,n) & \text{if } \sin(\frac{\pi}{2}m) + n < 1, \\ 1 & \text{if } \sin(\frac{\pi}{2}m) + n \geq 1. \end{cases}$		$J_{2L}(m,n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \geq n, \\ \min\{n, \frac{2}{\pi} \arcsin(1-m)\} & \text{if } m < n. \end{cases}$	
		$J_{2R}(m,n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \geq n, \\ \min\{n, 1 - \sin(\frac{\pi}{2}m)\} & \text{if } m < n. \end{cases}$	
$PS_3(m,n) = \begin{cases} \max(m,n) & \text{if } m^2 + n^3 < 1, \\ 1 & \text{if } m^2 + n^3 \geq 1. \end{cases}$		$J_{3L}(m,n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \geq n, \\ \min\{n, \sqrt{1-m^3}\} & \text{if } m < n. \end{cases}$	
		$J_{3R}(m,n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \geq n, \\ \min\{n, \sqrt[3]{1-m^2}\} & \text{if } m < n. \end{cases}$	
$PS_4(m,n) = \begin{cases} \max(m,n) & \text{if } m + \sqrt{n} < 1, \\ 1 & \text{if } m + \sqrt{n} \geq 1. \end{cases}$		$J_{4L}(m,n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \geq n, \\ \min\{n, 1-\sqrt{m}\} & \text{if } m < n. \end{cases}$	
		$J_{4R}(m,n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \geq n, \\ \min\{n, (1-m)^2\} & \text{if } m < n. \end{cases}$	

Example 3.5 Suppose that PT_i ($i=1,2,3,4$) are pseudo-t-norms as shown in **Example 3.3** and PS_i ($i=1,2,3,4$) are pseudo-s-norms as shown in **Example 3.4**. Then, the binary function PT_i ($i=1,2,3,4,5,6$) defined on D^* are NPTs as follows:

(1) $PT_1(m,n) = (PT_1(m_1, n_1), PS_1(m_2, n_2), PS_1(m_3, n_3));$

- (2) $PT_2(m, n) = (PT_2(m_1, n_1), PS_2(m_2, n_2), PS_2(m_3, n_3));$
- (3) $PT_3(m, n) = (PT_3(m_1, n_1), PS_3(m_2, n_2), PS_3(m_3, n_3));$
- (4) $PT_4(m, n) = (PT_4(m_1, n_1), PS_4(m_2, n_2), PS_4(m_3, n_3));$
- (5) $PT_5(m, n) = (PT_1(m_1, n_1), PS_2(m_2, n_2), PS_3(m_3, n_3));$
- (6) $PT_6(m, n) = (PT_1(m_1, n_1), PS_3(m_2, n_2), PS_3(m_3, n_3)).$

Example 3.6 Suppose that PT_i ($i=1,2,3,4$) are pseudo-t-norms as shown in **Example 3.3** and PS_i ($i=1,2,3,4$) are pseudo-s-norms as shown in **Example 3.4**. Then, the binary function PS_i ($i=1,2,3,4,5,6$) defined on D^* are NPSs as follows:

- (1) $PS_1(m, n) = (PS_1(m_1, n_1), PT_1(m_2, n_2), PT_1(m_3, n_3));$
- (2) $PS_2(m, n) = (PS_2(m_1, n_1), PT_2(m_2, n_2), PT_2(m_3, n_3));$
- (3) $PS_3(m, n) = (PS_3(m_1, n_1), PT_3(m_2, n_2), PT_3(m_3, n_3));$
- (4) $PS_4(m, n) = (PS_4(m_1, n_1), PT_4(m_2, n_2), PT_4(m_3, n_3));$
- (5) $PS_5(m, n) = (PS_1(m_1, n_1), PT_2(m_2, n_2), PT_3(m_3, n_3));$
- (6) $PS_6(m, n) = (PS_1(m_1, n_1), PT_3(m_2, n_2), PT_3(m_3, n_3)).$

Theorem 3.7 Give a binary function $PT: D^* \times D^* \rightarrow D^*$, two pseudo-s-norms PS_i ($i=1,2$) and a pseudo-t-norm PT . Then, $\forall m, n \in D^*$,

$$PT(m, n) = (PT(m_1, n_1), PS_1(m_2, n_2), PS_2(m_3, n_3))$$

is a NPT.

Proof. $\forall m, u, n, v, r \in D^*$, have following:

(NPT1) According to item (PT1) of **Definition 2.1** and item (PS1) of **Definition 2.2**, it is obvious that $PT(m, PT(n, r)) = PT(m, (PT(n_1, r_1), PS_1(n_2, r_2), PS_2(n_3, r_3))) = (PT(m_1, PT(n_1, r_1)), PS_1(m_2, PS_1(n_2, r_2)), PS_2(m_3, PS_2(n_3, r_3))) = (PT(n_1, PT(m_1, r_1)), PS_1(n_2, PS_1(m_2, r_2)), PS_2(n_3, PS_2(m_3, r_3))) = PT(n, PT(m, r));$

(NPT2) If $m \leq_1 u, n \leq_1 v$, then $PT(m_1, n_1) \leq PT(u_1, v_1), PS_1(m_2, n_2) \geq PS_1(u_2, v_2), PS_2(m_3, n_3) \geq PS_2(u_3, v_3)$. Therefore, $PT(m, n) \leq_1 PT(u, v)$. Likewise, we can also get $PT(n, m) \leq_1 PT(v, u)$.

(NPT3) $PT(m, 1_{D^*}) = (PT(m_1, 1), PS_1(m_2, 0), PS_2(m_3, 0)) = (m_1, m_2, m_3) = m$. Similarly, $PT(1_{D^*}, m) = m$.

Thus, $PT(m, n)$ is a NPT.

Theorem 3.8 Give a binary function $PS: D^* \times D^* \rightarrow D^*$, two pseudo-t-norms PT_i ($i=1,2$) and a pseudo-s-norm PS . Then,

$$PS(m, n) = (PS(m_1, n_1), PT_1(m_2, n_2), PT_2(m_3, n_3))$$

is a NPS, for arbitrary $m, n \in D^*$.

Theorem 3.7 provides a idea for constructing NPT on D^* with pseudo-s-norm and pseudo-t-norm. However, the reverse is not able to find two pseudo-s-norms PS_i ($i=1,2$) and pseudo-t-norm PT to make $PT = (PT, PS_1, PS_2)$.

In order to make a clear distinction between the two types of NPTs, so put forward a concept of RNPT.

Definition 3.9 If $\forall m, n \in D^*$, there exists two pseudo-s-norms PS_i ($i=1,2$) and a pseudo-t-norm PT such that PT holds with respect to the following equation:

$$PT(m, n) = (PT(m_1, n_1), PS_1(m_2, n_2), PS_2(m_3, n_3)).$$

Then PT is said to be representable.

Definition 3.10 If $\forall m, n \in D^*$, there exists pseudo-s-norm PS and pseudo-t-norm PT such that PT holds with respect to the following equation:

$$PT(m, n) = (PT(m_1, n_1), PS(m_2, n_2), PS(m_3, n_3)).$$

Then PT is said to be standard representable.

These NPTs given in **Example 3.5** are representable.

Definition 3.11 If $\forall m, n \in D^*$, there exists two pseudo-t-norms PT_i ($i=1,2$) and a pseudo-t-norm PS such that PS holds with respect to the following equation:

$$PS(m, n) = (PS(m_1, n_1), PT_1(m_2, n_2), PT_2(m_3, n_3)).$$

Then PS is said to be representable.

Definition 3.12 If $\forall m, n \in D^*$, there exists pseudo-s-norm PS and pseudo-t-norm PT such that PS holds with respect to the following equation:

$$PS(m, n) = (PS(m_1, n_1), PT(m_2, n_2), PT(m_3, n_3)).$$

Then PS is said to be standard representable.

These NPSs given in **Example 3.6** are representable.

Propositions 3.13 and **3.14** below demonstrate a approach to construct new RNPTs (RNPSs) with intuitionistic fuzzy t-norms (IFTs) and intuitionistic fuzzy s-norms (IFSs).

Proposition 3.13 $\forall x = (x_1, x_3) \in L, y = (y_1, y_3) \in L, T(x, y) = (t(x_1, y_1), s_2(x_3, y_3))$ is a representable IFT, which t and s_2 are t-norm and s-norm, respectively. If $\forall m, n \in D^*$, there is a pseudo-s-norm ps_1 that makes $0 \leq t(m_1, n_1) + ps_1(m_2, n_2) + s_2(m_3, n_3) \leq 3$ true, then $PT(m, n) = (t(m_1, n_1), ps_1(m_2, n_2), s_2(m_3, n_3))$ is a RNPT.

Proposition 3.14 $\forall x = (x_1, x_3) \in L, y = (y_1, y_3) \in L, S(x, y) = (s(x_1, y_1), t_2(x_3, y_3))$ is a representable IFS, where s and t_2 are s-norm and t-norm, respectively. If $\forall m, n \in D^*$, there is a pseudo-t-norm pt_1 that makes $0 \leq s(m_1, n_1) + pt_1(m_2, n_2) + t_2(m_3, n_3) \leq 3$ true, then $PS(m, n) = (s(m_1, n_1), pt_1(m_2, n_2), t_2(m_3, n_3))$ is a RNPS.

Example 3.15 ([20]) Table 3 below gives part t-norms, and its derived residual implications.

t-norms	Residual implications
$T_M(m, n) = \min(m, n)$	$I_{GD}(m, n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \leq n, \\ n & \text{if } m > n. \end{cases}$
$T_P(m, n) = m \cdot n$	$I_{GG}(m, n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m \leq n, \\ \frac{n}{m} & \text{if } m > n. \end{cases}$
$T_{LK}(m, n) = \max(m + n - 1, 0)$	$I_{LK}(m, n) = \min(1, 1 - m + n)$

Example 3.16 ([20]) Table 4 below gives part s-norms, and its derived residual co-implications.

s-norms	Residual co-implications
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$$\begin{array}{l}
 S_M(m, n) = \max(m, n) \\
 S_P(m, n) = m + n - m \cdot n \\
 S_{LK}(m, n) = \min(m + n, 1)
 \end{array}
 \qquad
 \begin{array}{l}
 J_{GD}(m, n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \geq n, \\ n & \text{if } m < n. \end{cases} \\
 J_{GG}(m, n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \geq n, \\ \frac{n-m}{1-m} & \text{if } m < n. \end{cases} \\
 J_{LK}(m, n) = \max(0, n - m)
 \end{array}$$

Example 3.17 Let PS_i ($i=1,2,4$) are pseudo-s-norms as shown in **Example 3.4**, T_M, T_P, T_{LK} are t-norms as shown in **Example 3.15**, and S_M, S_P, S_{LK} are s-norms as shown in **Example 3.16**. Then, the binary function PT_i ($i=7,8,9$) constructed by IFTs defined on D^* are RNPTs as follows:

- (1) $PT_7(m, n) = (T_M(m_1, n_1), PS_4(m_2, n_2), S_{LK}(m_3, n_3));$
- (2) $PT_8(m, n) = (T_P(m_1, n_1), PS_2(m_2, n_2), S_M(m_3, n_3));$
- (3) $PT_9(m, n) = (T_{LK}(m_1, n_1), PS_1(m_2, n_2), S_P(m_3, n_3)).$

Example 3.18 Let PT_i ($i=1,2,4$) are pseudo-t-norms as shown in **Example 3.3**, T_M, T_P, T_{LK} are t-norms as shown in **Example 3.15**, and S_M, S_P, S_{LK} are s-norms as shown in **Example 3.16**. Then, the binary function PS_i ($i=7,8,9$) constructed by IFSs defined on D^* are RNPSs as follows:

- (1) $PS_7(m, n) = (S_M(m_1, n_1), PT_4(m_2, n_2), T_{LK}(m_3, n_3));$
- (2) $PS_8(m, n) = (S_P(m_1, n_1), PT_2(m_2, n_2), T_M(m_3, n_3));$
- (3) $PS_9(m, n) = (S_{LK}(m_1, n_1), PT_1(m_2, n_2), T_P(m_3, n_3)).$

Definition 3.19 ([13]) A mapping $N: D^* \rightarrow D^*$ be known as NN if satisfies, $\forall m, n \in D^*$:

- (NN1) $m \leq_1 n$ iff $\geq_1 N(n)$;
- (NN2) $N(1_{D^*}) = 0_{D^*}$;
- (NN3) $N(0_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$.

If $N(N(m)) = m$ holds with $\forall m \in D^*$, then N is said to be involutive NN.

The function $Ns: D^* \rightarrow D^*$ defined by, $\forall (m_1, m_2, m_3) \in D^*$,

$$Ns(m_1, m_2, m_3) = (m_3, 1 - m_2, m_1)$$

is a involutive NN, which is also called standard NN. Meanwhile, $N(m) = (m_2, 1 - m_3, m_1)$, $N(x) = (m_2, m_1, m_1)$, $N(m) = (m_2, 1 - m_2, m_1)$ are NNs.

Definition 3.20 Assume that PT is a NPT, N is a NN and PS is a NPS. $\forall m, n \in D^*$, if the triple (PT, N, PS) satisfied the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N(PS(m, n)) &= PT(N(m), N(n)). \\
 N(PT(m, n)) &= PS(N(m), N(n));
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, we call the triple (PT, N, PS) is a DMNT.

Theorem 3.21 Suppose N is involutive. If exists a NPS PS , then such that PT be defined as

$$PT(m, n) = N(PS(N(m), N(n)))$$

is NPT. Besides, (PT, N, PS) is a DMNT.

Proof. According to known condition, there are as follows, $\forall m, u, n, v, r \in D^*$:

(NPT1) According to item (NPS1) of **Definition 3.2**, naturally there is $PT(m, PT(n, r)) = PT(m, N(PS(N(n), N(r)))) = N(PS(N(m), N(N(PS(N(n), N(r))))) = N(PS(N(m), PS(N(n), N(r)))) = N(PS(N(n), PS(N(m), N(r)))) = PT(n, PT(m, r)).$

(NPT2) If $m \leq u, n \leq v$, so $N(m) \geq N(u), N(n) \geq N(v)$. From (NPS2) of **Definition 3.2** and (NN1) of **Definition 3.19**, we get $PS(N(m), N(n)) \geq PS(N(u), N(v))$ and $PS(N(n), N(m)) \geq PS(N(v), N(u))$. Thus, $N(PS(N(m), N(n))) \leq N(PS(N(u), N(v)))$ and $N(PS(N(n), N(m))) \leq N(PS(N(v), N(u)))$, that is, $PT(m, n) \leq PT(u, v)$ and $PT(n, m) \leq PT(v, u)$.

(NPT3) $PT(1_{D^*}, m) = N(PS(N(1_{D^*}), N(m))) = N(PS(0_{D^*}, N(m))) = N(N(m)) = m$. Similarly, $PT(m, 1_{D^*}) = m$.

Therefore, the statement that PT is NPT is proved.
 Besides, (PT, N, PS) is a DMNT.

Theorem 3.22 Assume N is involutive. If exists a NPT PT , then such that PS be defined as

$$PS(m, n) = N(PT(N(m), N(n)))$$

being NPS. Moreover, (PT, N, PS) is a DMNT.

Example 3.23 A few NPTs and NPSs are dual about N_s .

(1) $PT_1(m, n) = (PT_1(m_1, n_1), PS_1(m_2, n_2), PS_1(m_3, n_3)), PS_1(m, n) = (PS_1(m_1, n_1), PT_1(m_2, n_2), PT_1(m_3, n_3))$.

Indeed, $PT_1(N_s(m), N_s(n)) = PT_1((m_3, 1-m_2, m_1), (n_3, 1-n_2, n_1)) = (PT_1(m_3, n_3), PS_1(1-m_2, 1-n_2), PS_1(m_1, n_1))$, then $N_s(PT_1(N_s(m), N_s(n))) = (PS_1(m_1, n_1), 1-PS_1(1-m_2, 1-n_2), PT_1(m_3, n_3)) = (PS_1(m_1, n_1), PT_1(m_2, n_2), PT_1(m_3, n_3)) = PS_1(m, n)$.

(2) $PT_3(m, n) = (PT_3(m_1, n_1), PS_3(m_2, n_2), PS_3(m_3, n_3)), PS_3(m, n) = (PS_3(m_1, n_1), PT_3(m_2, n_2), PT_3(m_3, n_3))$.

The theorem about UNPTs is given next:

Theorem 3.24 Let $PT: D^* \times D^* \rightarrow D^*$ being a function. $\forall m, n \in D^*$,

$$PT(m, n) = \begin{cases} m & n = 1_{D^*}, \\ n & m = 1_{D^*}, \\ (\min(2m_1, n_1), \max(1-2m_1, 1-n_1), \max(m_3, n_3)) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

is a UNPT.

Proof. First, we show that PT is a NPT, $\forall m, u, n, v, r \in D^*$.

(NPT1) If $m = 1_{D^*}$ or $n = 1_{D^*}$, then PT satisfies the associative law. If $m \neq 1_{D^*}, n \neq 1_{D^*}$, $PT(m, PT(n, r)) = (\min(2m_1, \min(2n_1, r_1)), \max(1-2m_1, 1-\min(2n_1, r_1)), \max(m_3, \max(n_3, r_3))) = (\min(2m_1, 2n_1, r_1), \max(1-2m_1, 1-2n_1, 1-r_1), \max(m_3, n_3, r_3)) = (\min(2n_1, \min(2m_1, r_1)), \max(1-2n_1, 1-\min(2m_1, r_1)), \max(n_3, \max(m_3, r_3))) = PT(n, PT(m, r))$.

(NPT2) If $m = 1_{D^*}$ or $n = 1_{D^*}$, we can prove PT is undecreasing in each variable. If $m \neq 1_{D^*}, n \neq 1_{D^*}$, at the same time satisfy $m \leq u, n \leq v$, and $m_1 \leq u_1, n_1 \leq v_1, m_3 \geq u_3, n_3 \geq v_3$. Thus, $\min(2m_1, n_1) \leq \min(2u_1, v_1)$, $\max(1-2m_1, 1-n_1) \geq \max(1-2u_1, 1-v_1)$, $\max(m_3, n_3) \geq \max(u_3, v_3)$. That is, $PT(m, n) \leq PT(u, v)$. Likewise, we can also have $PT(n, m) \leq PT(v, u)$.

(NPT3) $PT(m, 1_{D^*}) = m, PT(1_{D^*}, m) = m$. Therefore, PT is a NPT.

Second, assume NPT PT is representable, $m = (m_1, m_2, m_3) \in D^*, n = (n_1, n_2, n_3) \in D^*$, there are a pseudo-t-norm PT and two pseudo-s-norms $PS_i (i=1,2)$ such that $PT(m, n) = (PT(m_1, n_1), PS_1(m_2, n_2), PS_2(m_3, n_3))$. Let $m = (0.2, 0.5, 0.4), u = (0.4, 0.3, 0.2), n = (0.5, 0.7, 0.6)$. From $PT(m, n) = (0.4, 0.6, 0.6)$ and $PT(u, n) = (0.5, 0.5, 0.6)$, we get $PS_1(m_2, n_2) = 0.6$ and $PS_1(u_2, n_2) = 0.5$, so $PS_1(m_2, n_2) \neq PS_1(u_2, n_2)$. Thus $PS_1(m, n)$ is not independent from m_1 , that is to say PT is UNPT.

Moreover, $\forall m, n \in D^*$, the dual of NPT PT about standard NN N_s is NPS PS , which be defined as:

$$PS(m, n) = \begin{cases} m & n = 0_{D^*}, \\ n & m = 0_{D^*}, \\ (\max(m_1, n_1), \min(2m_3, n_3), \min(2m_3, n_3)) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then, PS is unrepresentable.

Remark 3.25 On the one hand, suppose PT and N_s are UNPT and standard NN on D^* , respectively. The dual of PT about N_s is PS . Then, we have that PS is UNPS. On the other hand, let N be involutive NN, the dual NPT about N of UNPS is unrepresentable.

4. NRI Induced by NPT on D^*

Definition 4.1 ([13]) A NI is a mapping $I: D^* \times D^* \rightarrow D^*$, $\forall m, u, n, v \in D^*$, if it satisfies:

(NI1) $m \leq_1 u \Rightarrow I(m, n) \geq_1 I(u, n)$;

(NI2) $n \leq_1 v \Rightarrow I(m, n) \leq_1 I(m, v)$;

(NI3) $I(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = I(0_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$;

(NI4) $I(1_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = 0_{D^*}$.

Since NPT without commutativity, we can define left and right NRIs which satisfy the residual property induced by NPT.

Definition 4.2 Let PT be a NPT. Define two functions $I^{(L)}, I^{(R)}: D^* \times D^* \rightarrow D^*$:

$$I^{(L)}(m, n) = \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, m) \leq_1 n\};$$

$$I^{(R)}(m, n) = \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(m, k) \leq_1 n\}.$$

Then, $I^{(L)}$ ($I^{(R)}$) is called left NRI (right NRI) induced by PT .

We note that the two NRIs induced by PT as $I_{PT}^{(L)}, I_{PT}^{(R)}$.

Besides, Let PT be a NPT, then $\forall m, n, k \in D^*$, PT satisfies the residual criteria iff

$$PT(k, m) \leq_1 n \text{ iff } k \leq_1 I_{PT}^{(L)}(m, n);$$

$$PT(m, k) \leq_1 n \text{ iff } k \leq_1 I_{PT}^{(R)}(m, n).$$

Likewise, the concept of neutrosophic co-implications (NCIs) and related knowledge are also given as follows:

Definition 4.3 ([13]) A NCI is a binary function $J: (D^*)^2 \rightarrow D^*$, $\forall m, u, n, v \in D^*$, if it satisfies:

(NJ1) $m \leq_1 u \Rightarrow J(m, n) \geq_1 J(u, n)$;

(NJ2) $n \leq_1 v \Rightarrow J(m, n) \leq_1 J(m, v)$;

(NJ3) $J(0_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = J(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = 0_{D^*}$;

(NJ4) $J(0_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$.

Analogously, we can also define left and right neutrosophic residual co-implications (NRCIs) which satisfy the residual property induced by NPS.

Definition 4.4 Suppose that PS is a NPS. Define two functions $J^{(L)}, J^{(R)}: D^* \times D^* \rightarrow D^*$:

$$J^{(L)}(m, n) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, PS(k, m) \geq_1 n\};$$

$$J^{(R)}(m, n) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, PS(m, k) \geq_1 n\}.$$

Then, $J^{(L)}$ ($J^{(R)}$) is called left NRCI (right NRCI) induced by PS .

We remark that two NRCIs induced by PS as $J_{PS}^{(L)}, J_{PS}^{(R)}$.

Let PS be a NPS, then $\forall m, n, k \in D^*$, PS satisfies the residual criteria iff

$$PS(k, m) \geq_1 n \text{ iff } k \geq_1 J_{PS^{(L)}}(m, n);$$

$$PS(m, k) \geq_1 n \text{ iff } k \geq_1 J_{PS^{(R)}}(m, n).$$

Through learning above definitions, we give the NRIs (NRCIs) of NPTs (NPSs) discussed in Section 3 as follows:

Example 4.5 Suppose that I_{iL} ($i=1,2,3,4$) and I_{iR} ($i=1,2,3,4$) are left and right residual implications induced by pseudo-t-norms PT_i ($i=1,2,3,4$) as shown in **Example 3.3**; J_{iL} ($i=1,2,3,4$) and J_{iR} ($i=1,2,3,4$) are left and right residual co-implications induced by pseudo-s-norms PS_i ($i=1,2,3,4$) as shown in **Example 3.4**. Then, the binary functions $I_{PT_i}^{(L)}$ ($i=1,2,3,4,5,6$) and $I_{PT_i}^{(R)}$ ($i=1,2,3,4,5,6$) induced by RNPTs PT_i ($i=1,2,3,4,5,6$) of **Example 3.5** defined on D^* are left and right NRIs as follows:

- (1) $I_{PT_1}^{(L)}(m, n) = (I_{1L}(m_1, n_1), J_{1L}(m_2, n_2), J_{1L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $I_{PT_1}^{(R)}(m, n) = (I_{1R}(m_1, n_1), J_{1R}(m_2, n_2), J_{1R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (2) $I_{PT_2}^{(L)}(m, n) = (I_{2L}(m_1, n_1), J_{2L}(m_2, n_2), J_{2L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $I_{PT_2}^{(R)}(m, n) = (I_{2R}(m_1, n_1), J_{2R}(m_2, n_2), J_{2R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (3) $I_{PT_3}^{(L)}(m, n) = (I_{3L}(m_1, n_1), J_{3L}(m_2, n_2), J_{3L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $I_{PT_3}^{(R)}(m, n) = (I_{3R}(m_1, n_1), J_{3R}(m_2, n_2), J_{3R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (4) $I_{PT_4}^{(L)}(m, n) = (I_{4L}(m_1, n_1), J_{4L}(m_2, n_2), J_{4L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $I_{PT_4}^{(R)}(m, n) = (I_{4R}(m_1, n_1), J_{4R}(m_2, n_2), J_{4R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (5) $I_{PT_5}^{(L)}(m, n) = (I_{1L}(m_1, n_1), J_{2L}(m_2, n_2), J_{3L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $I_{PT_5}^{(R)}(m, n) = (I_{1R}(m_1, n_1), J_{2R}(m_2, n_2), J_{3R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (6) $I_{PT_6}^{(L)}(m, n) = (I_{1L}(m_1, n_1), J_{3L}(m_2, n_2), J_{3L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $I_{PT_6}^{(R)}(m, n) = (I_{1R}(m_1, n_1), J_{3R}(m_2, n_2), J_{3R}(m_3, n_3)).$

Example 4.6 Suppose that I_{iL} ($i=1,2,3,4$) and I_{iR} ($i=1,2,3,4$) are left and right residual implications induced by pseudo-t-norms PT_i ($i=1,2,3,4$) as shown in **Example 3.3**; J_{iL} ($i=1,2,3,4$) and J_{iR} ($i=1,2,3,4$) are left and right residual co-implications induced by pseudo-s-norms PS_i ($i=1,2,3,4$) as shown in **Example 3.4**. Then, the binary functions $J_{PS_i}^{(L)}$ ($i=1,2,3,4,5,6$) and $J_{PS_i}^{(R)}$ ($i=1,2,3,4,5,6$) induced by RNPSs PS_i ($i=1,2,3,4,5,6$) of **Example 3.6** defined on D^* are left and right NRCIs as follows:

- (1) $J_{PS_1}^{(L)}(m, n) = (J_{1L}(m_1, n_1), I_{1L}(m_2, n_2), I_{1L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $J_{PS_1}^{(R)}(m, n) = (J_{1R}(m_1, n_1), I_{1R}(m_2, n_2), I_{1R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (2) $J_{PS_2}^{(L)}(m, n) = (J_{2L}(m_1, n_1), I_{2L}(m_2, n_2), I_{2L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $J_{PS_2}^{(R)}(m, n) = (J_{2R}(m_1, n_1), I_{2R}(m_2, n_2), I_{2R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (3) $J_{PS_3}^{(L)}(m, n) = (J_{3L}(m_1, n_1), I_{3L}(m_2, n_2), I_{3L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $J_{PS_3}^{(R)}(m, n) = (J_{3R}(m_1, n_1), I_{3R}(m_2, n_2), I_{3R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (4) $J_{PS_4}^{(L)}(m, n) = (J_{4L}(m_1, n_1), I_{4L}(m_2, n_2), I_{4L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $J_{PS_4}^{(R)}(m, n) = (J_{4R}(m_1, n_1), I_{4R}(m_2, n_2), I_{4R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (5) $J_{PS_5}^{(L)}(m, n) = (J_{1L}(m_1, n_1), I_{2L}(m_2, n_2), I_{3L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $J_{PS_5}^{(R)}(m, n) = (J_{1R}(m_1, n_1), I_{2R}(m_2, n_2), I_{3R}(m_3, n_3));$
- (6) $J_{PS_6}^{(L)}(m, n) = (J_{1L}(m_1, n_1), I_{3L}(m_2, n_2), I_{3L}(m_3, n_3));$
 $J_{PS_6}^{(R)}(m, n) = (J_{1R}(m_1, n_1), I_{3R}(m_2, n_2), I_{3R}(m_3, n_3)).$

Because NPS PS are dual operator of NPT PT about Ns , so the NRIs induced by NPT and the NRCIs induced by NPS are dual. For **Examples 3.5** and **3.6** given above, If PS and PT are dual, then the NRCIs J_{ps} derived by PS is the dual operator of the NRIs I_{PT} induced by PT .

The following we will show an important theorem which proves sufficient conditions that the residual operator derived by a NPT is always a NI.

Theorem 4.7 Assume PT be a NPT on D^* . Then, $\forall m, n \in D^*$,

$$I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n) = \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, m) \leq_1 n\};$$

$$I_{PT^{(R)}}(m, n) = \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(m, k) \leq_1 n\}.$$

are NIs.

Proof. First give the proof that $I_{PT^{(L)}}$ is a NI, $\forall m, u, n, v \in D^*$:

We get $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, 1_{D^*}) = \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, m) \leq_1 1_{D^*}\} = 1_{D^*}$ by **Definition 4.2**. Thus we have $I_{PT^{(L)}}(1_{D^*}, 1_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$. From (NPT2) in **Definition 3.1**, we get $I_{PT^{(L)}}(1_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, 1_{D^*}) \leq_1 0_{D^*}\} = 0_{D^*}$. $I_{PT^{(L)}}(0_{D^*}, 0_{D^*}) = \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, 0_{D^*}) \leq_1 0_{D^*}\} = 1_{D^*}$.

If $m \leq_1 u$. By (NPT2) in **Definition 3.1**, $\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, m) \leq_1 n\} \supseteq_1 \{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, u) \leq_1 n\}$, then $\sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, m) \leq_1 n\} \geq_1 \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, u) \leq_1 n\}$. Thus, $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n) \geq_1 I_{PT^{(L)}}(u, n)$.

If $n \leq_1 v$. Since the undecreasingness of PT , we have $\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, m) \leq_1 n\} \subseteq_1 \{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, m) \leq_1 v\}$, then $\sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, m) \leq_1 n\} \leq_1 \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, m) \leq_1 v\}$. Thus, $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n) \leq_1 I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, v)$.

To sum up, $I_{PT^{(L)}}$ is a NI. Likewise, $I_{PT^{(R)}}$ is a NI can also be proved.

Some relevant properties of NRI are given below.

Theorem 4.8 Suppose that PT be a NPT on D^* , $I_{PT^{(L)}}$, $I_{PT^{(R)}}$ are NRIs. Then, for $\forall m, n, r \in D^*$,

- (1) $I_{PT^{(L)}}(0_{D^*}, n) = 1_{D^*}$;
- (2) $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, 1_{D^*}) = 1_{D^*}$;
- (3) $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, m) = 1_{D^*}$;
- (4) $I_{PT^{(L)}}(1_{D^*}, n) = n$;
- (5) $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n) \geq_1 n$;
- (6) $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n) = 1_{D^*}$ iff $m \leq_1 n$;
- (7) $I_{PT^{(L)}}(PT(m, n), PT(m, r)) \geq_1 I_{PT^{(L)}}(n, r)$;
- (8) $m \leq_1 I_{PT^{(L)}}(n, PT(m, n))$.

Similarly, $I_{PT^{(R)}}$ also satisfies the properties (1)-(7) in **Theorem 4.8**. However, it should be noted that NI induced by NPT, because pseudo-t-norm removes commutativity, leads to the difference in property (8) in the corresponding **Theorem 4.8** of $I_{PT^{(R)}}$, as shown below:

- (8) $m \leq_1 I_{PT^{(R)}}(n, PT(n, m))$.

Proof. The proofs of (1)-(4) are straightforward to obtain by **Definition 4.2**, so the proof is ignored.

(5) From (NI1) in **Definition 4.1**, we get that $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n) \geq_1 I_{PT^{(L)}}(1_{D^*}, n) = n$.

(6) (\Rightarrow) if $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n) = 1_{D^*}$, then $PT(1_{D^*}, m) \leq_1 n$. Thus, $m \leq_1 n$. (\Leftarrow) since $m \leq_1 n$, $PT(1_{D^*}, m) \leq_1 n$. Thus, $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n) \geq_1 1_{D^*}$, that is $I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n) = 1_{D^*}$.

(7) $I_{PT^{(L)}}(PT(m, n), PT(m, r)) = \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, PT(m, n)) \leq_1 PT(m, r)\} = \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(m, k) \leq_1 PT(m, r)\} \geq_1 \sup\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(k, n) \leq_1 r\} = I_{PT^{(L)}}(n, r)$.

(8) Since $PT(m, n) \leq_1 PT(m, n)$, so we get $m \leq_1 I_{PT^{(L)}}(n, PT(m, n))$.

The proof which $I_{PT^{(R)}}$ satisfies the properties (1)-(8) is similar to the proof of $I_{PT^{(L)}}$.

In the same way, we give two theorems about NPS on D^*

Theorem 4.9 Let PS be a NPS on D^* . Then, $\forall m, n \in D^*$,

$$J_{PS^{(L)}}(m, n) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, PS(k, m) \geq_1 n\};$$

$$J_{PS^{(R)}}(m, n) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, PS(m, k) \geq_1 n\}.$$

are NCIs.

Proof. According to the **Definition 4.4**, we can use the proof of **Theorem 4.7** method to prove it.

Theorem 4.10 Let PS is a NPS on D^* , $J_{PS^{(L)}}$, $J_{PS^{(R)}}$ are NRCIs. Then, $\forall m, n, r \in D^*$,

- (1) $J_{PS^{(L)}}(1_{D^*}, n) = 0_{D^*}$;
- (2) $J_{PS^{(L)}}(m, 0_{D^*}) = 0_{D^*}$;
- (3) $J_{PS^{(L)}}(m, m) = 0_{D^*}$;
- (4) $J_{PS^{(L)}}(0_{D^*}, n) = n$;
- (5) $J_{PS^{(L)}}(m, n) \leq_1 n$;
- (6) $J_{PS^{(L)}}(m, n) = 0_{D^*}$ iff $m \geq_1 n$;
- (7) $J_{PS^{(L)}}(PS(m, n), PS(m, r)) \leq_1 J_{PS^{(L)}}(n, r)$;
- (8) $m \geq_1 J_{PS^{(L)}}(n, PS(m, n))$.

Similarly, $J_{PS^{(R)}}$ also satisfies the properties (1)-(7) in **Theorem 4.10**. However, it should be noted that NCI induced by NPS, because pseudo-s-norm removes commutativity, leads to the difference in property (8) in the corresponding Theorem 4.10 of $J_{PS^{(R)}}$, as shown below:

- (8) $m \geq_1 J_{PS^{(R)}}(n, PS(n, m))$.

Definition 4.11 Let $I^{(L)}, I^{(R)}: D^* \times D^* \rightarrow D^*$ are NIs. $\forall m, n \in D^*$, the induced operators $PT_I^{(L)}, PT_I^{(R)}$ by $I^{(L)}, I^{(R)}$ are defined as follows:

$$PT_I^{(L)}(m, n) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq_1 I^{(L)}(n, k)\};$$

$$PT_I^{(R)}(m, n) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, n \leq_1 I^{(R)}(m, k)\}.$$

Theorem 4.12 Let $I^{(L)}, I^{(R)}$ are NIs on D^* . $\forall m, n, r \in D^*$, if $I^{(L)}, I^{(R)}$ satisfies below conditions:

- (a) $r \leq_1 I^{(L)}(n, m)$ iff $n \leq_1 I^{(R)}(r, m)$;
- (b) $I^{(L)}(m, I^{(L)}(n, r)) = I^{(L)}(n, I^{(L)}(m, r))$; $I^{(R)}(m, I^{(R)}(n, r)) = I^{(R)}(n, I^{(R)}(m, r))$;
- (c) $I^{(L)}(m, n) = 1_{D^*}$ iff $m \leq_1 n$; $I^{(R)}(m, n) = 1_{D^*}$ iff $m \leq_1 n$;
- (d) $I^{(L)}(1_{D^*}, m) = m$; $I^{(R)}(1_{D^*}, m) = m$.

Then, the induced operators $PT_I^{(L)}, PT_I^{(R)}$ by $I^{(L)}, I^{(R)}$ in Definition 4.11 are NPTs.

Proof. $\forall m, u, n, v \in D^*$, there are below:

(NPT1) From (1) and (2), $PT_I^{(L)}(m, PT_I^{(L)}(n, r)) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq_1 I^{(L)}(PT_I^{(L)}(n, r), k)\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT_I^{(L)}(n, r) \leq_1 I^{(R)}(m, k)\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, r \leq_1 I^{(R)}(n, I^{(R)}(m, k))\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, r \leq_1 I^{(R)}(m, I^{(R)}(n, k))\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT_I^{(L)}(m, r) \leq_1 I^{(R)}(n, k)\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, n \leq_1 I^{(L)}(PT_I^{(L)}(m, r), k)\} = PT_I^{(L)}(n, PT_I^{(L)}(m, r))$.

(NPT2) If $m \leq_1 u, n \leq_1 v$. So $I^{(L)}(v, k) \leq_1 I^{(L)}(n, k)$ for $\forall k \in D^*$. $\forall k_0 \in \{k \mid k \in D^*, u \leq_1 I^{(L)}(v, k)\}$, it can be concluded that $u \leq_1 I^{(L)}(v, k_0)$. Since $m \leq_1 u$, and $I^{(L)}(v, k_0) \leq_1 I^{(L)}(n, k_0)$, $m \leq_1 I^{(L)}(n, k_0)$, namely $k_0 \in \{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq_1 I^{(L)}(n, k)\}$. Thus, $\{k \mid k \in D^*, u \leq_1 I^{(L)}(v, k)\} \subseteq \{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq_1 I^{(L)}(n, k)\}$. Hence, $\inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq_1 I^{(L)}(n, k)\} \leq_1 \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, u \leq_1 I^{(L)}(v, k)\}$, that is, $PT_I^{(L)}(m, n) \leq_1 PT_I^{(L)}(u, v)$. Likewise, we can prove that $PT_I^{(L)}(n, m) \leq_1 PT_I^{(L)}(v, u)$.

(NPT3) $PT_I^{(L)}(1_{D^*}, m) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, 1_{D^*} \leq_1 I^{(L)}(m, k)\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, I^{(L)}(m, k) = 1_{D^*}\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq_1 k\} = m$; $PT_I^{(L)}(m, 1_{D^*}) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq_1 I^{(L)}(1_{D^*}, k)\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq_1 k\} = m$.

Therefore $PT_I^{(L)}$ is a NPT, and in the same way, we can also show that $PT_I^{(R)}$ is a NPT.

Theorem 4.13 If PT is a NPT on D^* , so there is $PT = PT_I^{(L)} = PT_I^{(R)}$.

Proof. $\forall m, n \in D^*$, from **Definitions 4.2** and **4.11**, we get $PT_I^{(L)}(m, n) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq_1 I^{(L)}(n, k)\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(m, n) \leq_1 k\} = PT(m, n)$ and $PT_I^{(R)}(m, n) = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, n \leq_1 I^{(R)}(m, k)\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, PT(m, n) \leq_1 k\} = PT(m, n)$. Thus, $PT = PT_I^{(L)} = PT_I^{(R)}$.

Definition 4.14 ([21]) An algebraic system $S=(S; \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, \rightarrow, 0, 1)$ is said to be a NCRL, $\forall m, n, r \in S$, if S satisfies:

- (1) $(S; \wedge, \vee, 0, 1)$ be a bounded lattice on S , its corresponding order is \leq , 0 is minimal element and 1 is maximal element of S ;
- (2) $(S; \otimes, 1)$ be non-commutative monoid and its neutral element is 1;
- (3) $m \otimes n \leq r \Leftrightarrow m \leq n \rightarrow r \Leftrightarrow n \leq m \rightarrow r$.

Sections 3 and **4** focus on NPTs and their NRIs. Next, a NCRL is established, which is constructed from three neutrosophic logic operators.

Theorem 4.15 Suppose $(D^*; \wedge, \vee, \subset, 0_{D^*}, 1_{D^*})$ is a system and PT is a NPT on D^* . $\forall m, n \in D^*$, define the following three equations,:

$$m \otimes n = PT(m, n); m \rightarrow n = I_{PT^{(L)}}(m, n); m \rightarrow n = I_{PT^{(R)}}(m, n).$$

Then, $(D^*; \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, \rightarrow, 0_{D^*}, 1_{D^*})$ is NCRL.

Proof. First, by **Proposition 2.9**, we get that $(D^*; \wedge, \vee, 0_{D^*}, 1_{D^*})$ be a bounded lattice on D^* .

Second, the fact that $(D^*; \otimes, 1_{D^*})$ is non-commutative monoid is proved. (1) $m \otimes 1_{D^*} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq I^{(L)}(1_{D^*}, k)\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq k\} = m$ and $1_{D^*} \otimes m = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, 1_{D^*} \leq I^{(L)}(m, k)\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, I^{(L)}(m, k) = 1_{D^*}\} = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq k\} = m$, i.e. $\forall m \in D^*$, the equation $1_{D^*} \otimes m = m \otimes 1_{D^*} = m$ is true. (2) Theorem 4.13 proves that $PT^{(L)} = PT$ is a NPT. Thus, PT does not satisfy the commutative law. (3) From (NPT1) of **Definition 3.1**, \otimes satisfies the associative law.

Finally, $\forall m, n, k \in D^*$, we prove the below equivalence relation

$$m \otimes n \leq k \Leftrightarrow m \leq n \rightarrow k \Leftrightarrow n \leq m \rightarrow k$$

holds. On the one hand, by what we know about \otimes , there are $m \otimes n = \inf\{k \mid k \in D^*, m \leq I^{(L)}(n, k)\}$, $m \otimes n \leq k$. Thus, there are $n \leq m \rightarrow k$ and $m \leq n \rightarrow k$. On the other hand, by what we know about \rightarrow , we get $n \rightarrow k = \sup\{t \mid t \in D^*, PT(t, n) \leq k\}$. Since $m \leq n \rightarrow k$, therefore $m \otimes n \leq k$. Likewise, there are $n \leq m \rightarrow k \Rightarrow m \otimes n \leq k$.

Thus, $(D^*; \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, \rightarrow, 0_{D^*}, 1_{D^*})$ is NCRL.

5. Conclusions

Neutrosophic logic is an important part of NS theory. Common neutrosophic logic operators are: NPTs, NPSs NIs, NNs and so on. On the basis of complete lattice $(D^*; \leq)$, We defined NPTs, NNs, NPSs and so on. In addition, DMNTs are defined, describing that NPT and NPS are dual with regard to the standard NN. Then, on the basis of complete lattice $(D^*; \leq)$, the concepts of NRI and NRCI is given, and we present a theorem which states that residual operator derived by NPTs must be NIs, and further study their fundamental properties. Finally, we provide a method to get NPT from NI and construct NCRLs. In the future, we will investigate neutrosophic inference methods and neutrosophic pseudo overlap functions based on some new results [22-33]. and further study their fundamental properties.

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